

CLASH AND COMPLEXITY OF THE BRITISH AND THE DOGRA INTERESTS

A CASE STUDY OF CENTRAL ASIAN AFFAIRS (1846-1885)

¹Sajad Ahmad Rather

¹Ph.D. Research Scholar, Department of History,
University of Kashmir, Srinagar, India

Abstract: When Punjab was annexed in 1846 AD, Kashmir was handed over to the Gulab Singh through the famous treaty of Amritsar. It is believed that main motive of British to hand over Kashmir to Gulab Singh was to lessen the force of the Sikhs and Afghans because North-West Frontier and Afghanistan problem was yet unsettled. Though, they were successful in checking the Punjab and Afghan threat but during the seventies of nineteenth century, Czarist Russia had her covetous eyes on the Kashmir Valley whose conquest would give her an opportunity to directly confront the British regime in India. The British administrators on the other hand wanted to check the expansion policy of the Russians and began to secure scientific borders wherever Russian peril was possible and this made British intervention in Kashmir inevitable. The present paper attempts to highlight the clash and complexities of the relationship between the British colonial power and Dogra maharajas of the princely state of Jammu and Kashmir. The main focus of this paper is to highlight the British imperialist quest for a scientific frontier and in this process how policy towards Kashmir was backed by both political as well as commercial interests.

Keywords: Kashmir, British, Dogra-state, Czarist Russia, Central-Asia, Political interest, Resident.

I. Introduction

The name “Central Asia” correctly describes, in a geographical sense, the heart of the continent. It is known from the sources that from countless ages, great caravans have passed from India right up to central Asia through the state.¹ In modern times Russia has come to dominate central Asia. Britain and Japan, based on India and China respectively too have made an impact on its modern history and politics.²

The AMRITSAR Treaty of 1846, through which Maharaja Gulab Singh acquired Kashmir from the British, had some special features. According to it, Kashmir was ceded to him forever and in independent possession.³ Unlike treaties with other Indian rulers, it contained “no clause prohibiting independent diplomatic intercourse with foreign powers.”⁴ In other words, the treaty gave Maharaja Gulab Singh large measure of independence, both in his internal and external affairs. But hardly the ink of the treaty was dry when the British Govt. of India started violating it by interfering in the affairs of the state.

II. Leaf Forward Policy: Events and Developments

The Dogra interests in Central Asian affairs arose during the Middle of the thirties of the 19th century when Gulab Singh, as an ambitious vassal of the Sikh kingdom of Lahore first subjugated Ladakh and Baltistan between 1834 and 1840 and then move towards Yarkand and Kashghar. He ultimately invaded western Tibet and then penetrated into the Lhasa territory. It is said from the very beginning the Dogra rulers followed a ‘forward policy’ in the Central Asia mainly for two reasons. Firstly, for the safety and security of their borders, the Dogra rulers had always described to push their northern frontier’s more north wards. At the same time such a policy might have been further strengthened by the economic factor, the Central Asian trade, particularly the lucrative shawl wool from Yarkand and U –TSANG which fed all the shawl and carpet industries in Kashmir secondly, the clash of interests of their over-lords with their own had always driven the

Dogra chiefs to look for allies in Central Asian Countries. The anti- Dogra attitude of Ranjit Singh successors compelled him to probe for friends in Yarkand and Nepal and they might have cherished some distant hope of forming an anti -Lahore as well as anti-British alliance with some Central Asian powers.⁵

It may be noted that at the time of the signing of the treaty of Amritsar, Gulab Singh had assured the British that he would be able to occupy Kashmir without any difficulty.⁶ But he did not know that as regards Kashmir, he only became the *de-jure* sovereign of Kashmir and a bitter opposition awaited him.⁷ The officers of the E.I.C. resented the transfer of Kashmir to him as well as at the measure of autonomy exercised by him. They try to curb his powers but Gulab Singh successfully resisted all their attempts. He asserted independence of Action by conquering Gilgit and Astor and by invading other Dard republics.

With the accession of Maharaja Ranbir Singh, the relationship underwent great transformation as is clear from 1858, the imperialist officers of the British crown were more vocal in denouncing the company's action of transforming Kashmir to Dogras, and a fresh tained of hatred against the rulers of Jammu and Kashmir engulfed the Anglo-India press. Also the sort of interference the British Government sought to impose in internal administration of the state was so outrageous that the Maharaja was not only compelled to conclude that the British officer an special duty was dealing in matters of trade as if Kashmir was a part of British territory,⁸ but the Dogra ruler was also driven helplessly to seek political alliances with Central Asia and Russia under the scare that the Governor General and his colleagues were planning of some pretext to subvert his state and authority.

Under these conditions Ranbir Singh could not remain a silent spectator of these political moves which were taking place in his territories. He sent his trusted agents to explore the vast regions of Central Asia and Persia to know the events taking place there and also to establish relations with these countries.⁹ Mehta Sher Singh was sent on a special survey Mission to Central Asian countries ,who left Srinagar on 28th July 1866 and visited 175 places including Hazara, Peshawar, Kabul, Samarkand, Kashghar and Yarkand and came back via Leh in October, 1867 with interesting account of geographical and economic conditions and political transactions of these regions.¹⁰ Fully equipped with the facts and figures, Maharaja Ranbir Singh move his forces towards Yarkand which had been the cherished object to the "Forward Policy" of the Dogras since Gulab Singh's days. Taking advantage of the disturbed political conditions there he asked permission of British government, to dispatch military expedition to Yarkand and Kashghar in order to incorporate these famous cities into his own dominions.¹¹

British who had already begun to cast doubts on the loyalty of the Maharaja Ranbir Singh, did not countenance his military occupation of that Central Asian Post and sent him a strong note of disapproval. As they had formulated their own plans for a long- term policy of commercial penetration to, and subsequent political domination of Central Asia.¹²

To cut the roots of Ranbir Singh influence in Central Asia and to isolate him from northern powers, the British devised to draw a wedge between him and Russia and china in the shape of sharp-edged commercial policy, cunningly inveigling even unsuspecting Ranbir Singh in their game. As soon as the Maharaja directed the Yarkandi envoy to see the viceroy, which he did, the British government used it to blame him of Clandestine seditions with foreign powers and to send the famous mission of Douglas Forsythe to Central Asia which paved the way for replacing the Dogra influence in those territories by that of the British. Also the Maharaja was asked to provide all facilities to the Mission and make all arrangements regarding transport, supplies and accommodation as well.¹³

On the successful termination of the mission the Maharaja was further pressed to conclude with the British a commercial treaty in 1873, according to which a British Joint Commissioner was appointed at Leh to look after the up keep of roads and ensure the safety of travellers to Central Asia. Under the treaty he could not levy any toll or duty on goods sent from British India or abroad to Central Asia and vice-versa. Thus, with the appointment of the British Joint Commissioner in Ladakh and a political officer in Gilgit was ushered in a period of total British domination of all the foreign relations of Kashmir, with the Govt. in Central Asia and Tibet. In the same contract, a British trade officer was appointed in Kashghar who curiously enough designated as ‘Special Assistant to Kashmir Resident for Chinese affairs.’¹⁴ Another irritant in British Dogra relations was the clash of interests of both sides in Gilgit and Shinaki principalities.¹⁵

Kashmir was then the meeting place of the three greatest Empires of the East- the British, the Russia and the Chinese. But Kashmir was not only the meeting place of the three greatest empires it also lay in close proximity to Afghanistan and give her a strategic importance not possessed by any other state in India. It was, therefore rightly described as “the Sentry State “of the British Indian Empire.¹⁶

As a result of all this, the whole conduct of relations with Central Asian territories, both commercial and political, passed into the hands of the British. The Leap forward policy of the Maharaja was given up and in future, he was asked to refrain from such wild adventures. The British succeeded in to the imperial interests, counter moves of the British had attained almost complete success.¹⁷

III. Conclusion

From the above mentioned facts, we came to the conclusion that the result of all this and many other similar developments was such that as before the end of 1890 A.D., the independence of Dogra rulers became a thing of the past because they were reduced to the mere figure heads and their state became virtually a British dependency. The British diplomacy of commercial Missions and trade treaties with Central Asia Countries and with reluctant Dogra ruler, was more actuated by Political motives than by actual business interests. Thus, it becomes clear that the British state used one policy or other to limit the territory as well as to curb the power of the Dogra rulers. All this shows even the activities of the Dogra rulers within their own territories could not go on unwatched to a great extent.

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